

Enhancing Inclusive Education in English Language Teaching (ELT) for Students with Disabilities in India

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Abstract

Learning is the process of acquiring knowledge and encourages the development of critical thinking. Typically, students acquire knowledge through either traditional in-person methods or through digital platforms, often in a collaborative setting. Inclusive education refers to a collaborative learning environment where individuals engage with one another, both as teachers and learners. This article analyses the necessary conditions for inclusive education to increase the knowledge and understanding of English language teachers in India on how to cater to the specific needs of students with disabilities in English language teaching (ELT) classes. To address pedagogical and theoretical concerns, a range of materials are utilised, including experiential studies and UNESCO texts as inputs. The essay proposes practical and feasible techniques to make inclusive teaching a valuable tool in English Language Teaching (ELT) programs for students with disabilities. The study also examines other approaches based on the extent and progress of inclusive education. In India, numerous mainstream schools and universities have not yet embraced inclusive education.

Keywords: Inclusive education, pedagogy, theory, strategy, disability, training.

Introduction

The World Health Organisation reports that there are one billion individuals who have disabilities. More than 500 million children are impaired due to mental, physical, or sensory disability. Children are constrained by both physical and social obstacles. Additionally, their disabilities isolate them from society and hinder their active involvement in the progress of their country. Every youngster possesses the entitlement to receive an education, as they represent the forthcoming members of society. Furthermore, the guiding idea is to ensure that

individuals experience a sense of welcome, are presented with suitable challenges, and receive adequate support in their endeavours.

Inclusive education ensures the provision of high-quality education that is accessible to all pupils, regardless of handicap. Special Needs Education is a notion that encompasses the idea that education should be accessible to all students, regardless of whatever difficulties they may have. For non-English speakers, ELT lessons provide a difficult problem for both teachers and learners. To prevent academic failures among kids with disabilities, teachers must provide specific attention to improve their academic performance.

An inclusive English Language Teaching (ELT) class requires the instructor to possess flexibility, creativity, a willingness to learn from the students, and the ability to facilitate active learning. The English Language Teaching (ELT) instructor must adopt and implement efficient pedagogical strategies and methodologies. In addition, it is essential for the individual to meticulously and creatively choose acceptable resources, develop appropriate assignments, and employ effective classroom management techniques to meet the distinct educational requirements of children with special needs. They need to be knowledgeable about the characteristics, origins, evaluation, and interventions for students with disabilities (Hallahan et al., 2004).

Defining Inclusive Education

Inclusive education can be understood and interpreted in several ways, such as a belief, philosophy, or even as a 'position' (Dukes & Berlingo, 2020). Several nations worldwide are preoccupied with the issue of inclusive education.

Despite the considerable focus on this topic, a comprehensive analysis of the literature and implementation of Inclusive Education demonstrates the absence of a universally accepted and widely recognised concept in this subject. The phrase has acquired a context-specific meaning, varying from person to person.

The definition of Inclusive Education differs from one country to another and is linked to various viewpoints that reflect the interests of each region. In addition to the terminology, educators also examine how this concept is linked to specific pedagogical methods that are necessary to accomplish educational goals. They define educational requirements based on what is necessary for students to achieve specific educational objectives (Mittler & Daunt,

1995). An exhaustive literature assessment of several research revealed that the majority of teachers held either neutral or unfavourable opinions towards Inclusive Education (De Boer, Pijl & Minnaert, 2011). The literature on Inclusive Education in India predominantly centres around the issues of children with disabilities. In a study, the author cites Chadha's definition of inclusion as the provision of equitable opportunities for all children, regardless of the type and severity of their disabilities, to receive effective educational services. This includes the provision of necessary supplementary aids and support services, and the placement of children in age-appropriate classes in their local schools (Singal, 2005).

"Inclusion is regarded as a systematic way to acknowledge and address the many needs and differences among individuals. It encompasses alterations and adjustments in content, methods, frameworks, and tactics, all guided by a shared vision." The objective of this initiative is to create a climate where both instructors and learners embrace diversity and view it as a source of growth and enrichment, rather than a difficulty. UNESCO has identified four essential components as the intrinsic characteristics of Inclusive Education in its guidelines manifesto.

From an educational perspective, these pronouncements can also be seen as providing education for students with special needs within mainstream schools. The successful execution of this endeavour is contingent upon the instructor variables, particularly their inclination to undertake this responsibility and their proficiency in executing it. It also refers to a system that includes a broad spectrum of students with different backgrounds and characteristics.

While it is possible to amalgamate these diverse concepts, there is no universally accepted definition for the concept of inclusion. The Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) issued by the United Nations strongly recommends that countries ensure the rights of individuals with disabilities by granting them equal access to education and preventing any form of discrimination. Additionally, it emphasises the need for an inclusive education system at all levels to promote lifelong learning. Even this convention fails to offer a conclusive response to the question of what Inclusive Education entails (Jokinen, 2018). Once we have made an effort to describe IE, we can now proceed to discuss the origin and development of IE.

Requirements for Successful Inclusion

There are no definitive blueprints for achieving widespread success in implementing Inclusive Education. Inclusive Education requires a constant process and a fundamental requirement is to have a strong awareness and comprehensive knowledge of the important advancements in this field. Its origins are derived from the influences in the formation of international human rights, as well as the institutions and documents that uphold them. To fully comprehend the distinction between inclusive education and other similar paradigms, one must grasp the underlying principles, structure, methodologies, and fundamental components that set it apart (Stubbs, 2008).

Several issues, including large class sizes, negative attitudes towards disability, exam-focused education systems, inadequate support services, rigid teaching methods, and limited parent engagement, influence the success of Inclusive Education.

Furthermore, there are additional factors, such as the improper execution of the implementation process, which involves various stakeholders such as supporting staff, education resource service providers, and teachers' attitudes. These factors also play a crucial role in determining the success of Inclusive Education (Magnússon, 2019). Hence, Inclusive Education should prioritise the educational requirements of pupils rather than fixating on their disability. Their education is not exceptional; rather, it is tailored to their specific needs.

The requirements for Inclusive Education are as follows:

1. **A Differentiated Curriculum:** This refers to a curriculum that is designed to cater to the unique abilities and demands of each student. The curriculum should deconstruct the subject into discrete instructional phases for teaching and learning.

2. **Resource Room:** A room overseen by a resource teacher should be furnished with educational resources such as Braille materials and Braille writing tools, magnifying lenses, eyeglasses, reading stands, books with large print, hearing aids, and speech training kits.

3. **An itinerant or peripatetic teacher,** who specialises in special needs education, should provide guidance and technical assistance to the regular teacher as required.

4. **Integration/Mainstreaming:** This phrase refers to the inclusion of students with special educational needs in standard education settings without requiring modifications to the curriculum.

Inclusive ELT Classes for Students with Special Needs in India:

The primary determinant for successful industrial engineering (IE) is infrastructure, as it is the sole factor that can enable the effective execution of IE. Educational institutions are required to furnish the necessary infrastructure, facilities, and services to accommodate students with impairments.

1. The building and other infrastructure should be modified to ensure accessibility for those with disabilities.

2. Sufficient personnel should be provided to meet the requirements of individuals with disabilities.

3. Institutions should modify their policies and procedures to support Inclusive Education. The kids should receive instruction in inclusive general classes and be provided with individualised support to enhance their reading, writing, organisational, speech, and language abilities. In addition, it is crucial to offer assistive technologies, advice, and other necessary services specifically tailored for students who are deaf, hard of hearing, or vision-impaired. Additionally, it is imperative to provide specialised educational instruction, as well as occupational and physical treatment, for kids who have physical disabilities. Furthermore, it is essential to make appropriate arrangements for special transportation services for these students (Garcia & Tyler, 2010).

Basic Requirements and Attitudes of the English Language Teachers

English educators should be aware that impairment might manifest at any point during an individual's development. Certain individuals are born with a disability, while others develop them during their upbringing. Having this insight is crucial to recognise children who have difficulties. The English Language Teacher in India will be instructing a wide range of students, including those with disabilities. The disabilities encompass students with physical, mental, emotional, behavioural, and learning difficulties. Before implementing a curriculum based on Special Education Needs (SEN) and Inclusive Education, it is essential to have a comprehensive understanding of the issue of disability in children. Handicap, disability, and

rehabilitation are enduring aspects of the human condition that teachers should appropriately address. English Language Teachers should possess the qualities of inclusivity, openness, and patience when it comes to addressing disability and diversity. Teachers should approach students with disabilities like they would any other child, recognising their abilities beyond their impairment and demonstrating respect and admiration for their equal rights as students.

The Need for Training the English Language Teacher

Teachers' training is a crucial aspect that contributes to the effectiveness of inclusive English Language Teaching (ELT) sessions. This factor would have a significant impact on the result of inclusive practices. For the Inclusive ELT lessons in India to be successful, it is imperative to enhance the proficiency of teachers. The government and leaders of Private Educational Institutions should ensure that teachers have access to courses related to the IE programme. If there is a lack of resources, special efforts should be made to develop courses that teach IE pedagogy and curricula. Currently, the governments in modern capitalist nation-states are actively supervising and promoting significant growth in special education needs (SEN) education and training systems (Tomlinson, 2012).

Developing nations such as India should prioritise not only the mere execution of inclusive education (IE) for students with special educational needs (SEN) but also offer comprehensive training to teachers to ensure its successful implementation.

The Impact of Inclusive Education in ELT Classes

The ramifications and consequences of implementing Inclusive Education in English Language Teaching (ELT) programs would extend beyond students with disabilities to encompass even those without impairments. Research studies have demonstrated that there is no negative impact on the academic performance of non-disabled pupils when they are placed in inclusive classrooms. Research has shown that inclusive English Language Teaching (ELT) classrooms, which incorporate teaching methods that cater to the individual needs of students with special needs through individualised instruction, are more successful in achieving positive outcomes (Bennett & Gallagher, 2013). Inclusive Education is a beneficial approach for pupils who have particular educational requirements.

Inclusive Curriculum for ELT Classes

The Inclusive Curriculum for English Language Teaching (ELT) classes should have adaptable strategies to effectively address the diverse skills and requirements of inclusive classrooms. If the teaching methods and curricula are rigid, there will be a shortage of appropriate instructional materials, and teachers will undoubtedly feel restricted in fulfilling their obligations. In inclusive ELT lessons, the curriculum should be tailored to accommodate both typical students and those with disabilities, such as visual or hearing impairments. Overall, the curriculum for ELT programs should include both procedures and content that enable students and teachers to collaborate effectively and achieve meaningful language learning for all students.

Resources for Inclusive ELT Curriculum

As previously said, the availability of educational resources for English Language Teaching (ELT) classrooms is crucial for the effective implementation of Inclusive Education in ELT lessons. The success of this endeavour hinges not only on effective organisation and the implementation of legislation, rules, and regulations but also on the availability of instructional resources in standard classrooms.

The adoption of Inclusive Education would face significant hurdles in terms of providing teaching and learning materials, equipment, and financial resources.

Several nations worldwide have used various cost-efficient measures to address the issue of limited resources, to promote Inclusive Education overall and specifically in English Language Teaching (Carter & Nunan, 2001). The initiatives consist of Train the Trainer modules for English Language Teachers, partnerships between universities and pre-service training institutions for teacher training, and the transformation of SEN schools into resource centres to offer specialised knowledge and assistance to groups of general education schools, where students with Special Needs participate in peer programs.

Inclusive ELT Strategies

Teaching English to kids with Special demands would be highly beneficial provided the teachers possess the necessary competence to address a wide range of demands. Improved differentiation of learning tasks and instructional materials can only be achieved through school-based intervention (Davies, 2004). Certain students may encounter specific challenges in acquiring proficiency in the English language and may want assistance in enhancing their

areas of deficiency using various techniques to overcome their obstacles. Students with impairments, including those who are hearing or visually impaired, may need alternate communication tools to overcome the challenges they encounter in using spoken or written language.

- Dhawan suggests that the following tactics are particularly beneficial for visually impaired pupils to acquire English language skills.
- The process of converting English textbooks and additional information into Braille for transmission.
- The utilisation of narrative techniques, vocal performance, and interactive dramatisation to enhance linguistic proficiency.
- The focus is on providing a detailed explanation of synonyms and homophones.
- Introduction of novel terminology and linguistic elements. Utilisation of exposition and experience sharing for individuals with visual impairments.
- The judicious application of language games, phonetic games, reading passages, constructing sentences, practising dialogues, producing reports, engaging in discussions, and recording recordings.

These tactics would be very effective in engaging students, particularly those with Special Needs. The source cited is Dhawan (2011).

Assessment and Evaluation in Inclusive ELT Classes

Regarding assessment in Inclusive ELT classrooms, there are various approaches, encompassing both conventional and contemporary methodologies. For instance, the evaluation of listening abilities often relies on the use of recorded spoken texts to gauge students' understanding. There are significant distinctions between written language and spoken language, as the grammatical features of written language differ greatly from those of spoken language. As a result, pupils can be evaluated based on their usage of language structures. The growth of the learners can be assessed based on the overall skills, talents, and values demonstrated by the students after each learning session. The examination and evaluation might be continuous. Each learner should be assessed individually based on their accomplishments rather than being compared to other learners. The evaluation in inclusive English Language Teaching (ELT) classrooms must occur in a versatile manner and within a

flexible timeframe and setting. It is important to understand that the way we evaluate our students has a significant impact on both their learning outcomes and the methods they use to learn (Brown et al., 2000). The Inclusive ELT classes should establish and implement an assessment methodology for evaluating students' progress both within and outside the classroom. Outside of the classroom, standardised tests can be utilised, while inside the classroom, tests can serve both formative and summative purposes.

In an inclusive classroom, English Language teachers need to prioritise the welfare of students when giving out homework assignments. This is particularly true if there is a need for substantial reading or writing. The teacher should provide an extended timeframe for the completion of both homework and tests.

If deemed essential, students with exceptional needs may be granted the opportunity to complete the examination in multiple sessions. The teacher can decrease the quantity of questions that students with Special Needs are required to answer.

In addition, they can offer alternative methods for assessing their understanding. Visually impaired pupils should be supplied with a scribe to assist them throughout written examinations, and the teacher may also assess them orally. The reference "Haque & Valeo, 2017" is provided.

Conclusion

The effectiveness of Inclusive ELT Classes for students with Special Needs relies on the comprehension and acknowledgement of the historical development and progression of Inclusive Education by both instructors and policymakers. They must respond to the diverse range of requirements of disabled students. This aim could be easily achieved through improved clarification of learning activities and the supply of educational resources. For this process to be carried out efficiently, it will require the teachers of English to receive specialised training, which will enable them to effectively implement inclusive teaching.

Without specialised training, English teachers would be unable to fulfil their expected duties. The teachers must receive training in the implementation of Inclusive Education to effectively meet the requirements of special kids. The teachers must adapt their teaching methods to align with various learning styles, including visual, auditory, and kinaesthetic.

It is imperative to adhere precisely to the requirements set forth by UNESCO and the UNO when designing, implementing, and evaluating Inclusive ELT lessons for both children with special needs and typically developing students. Indian society should universally acknowledge and embrace individuals with disabilities as integral members of the human race. Genuine appreciation for the variety of children with Special Needs guarantees their complete and equitable involvement in English Language Learning. It would lead to a sustainable and enduring process of acquiring knowledge and skills throughout one's life. 'Inclusive Education is a shift from teaching that focuses on the needs of the majority to learning that focuses on the needs of individual students' (Lesko et al., 2010).

One must transition from a teaching-centred curriculum to a curriculum that is centred around meeting specific needs.

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